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ROLE OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE, WORK-FAMILY CONFLICT, AND JOB PERFORMANCE AMONG UNIVERSITY TEACHERS

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Abstract

This study investigates the correlation between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict, and job performance of married female university teachers and whether spiritual intelligence and work-family conflict predict the job performance of married female university teachers or not. A self-constructed demographic questionnaire, meaning in life questionnaire (Steger, 2006) WFC scale by Carlson, et al. (2000) job performance self-rating questionnaire by Amin et. al., (2013) were administered to evaluate the correlation between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict & job performance. The sample consisted of 200 married female university teachers. (Mage=36.15, SD= 4.10) recruited from different universities of Lahore. Reliability was run along with Pearson's correlation and multiple Linear Regression and the result indicated a significant correlation between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict & and job performance of married female university teachers, and spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict emerged as analysts of job performance. Inclusive data on teachers' job performance is given by this study and accordingly, it will demonstrate a motivating force for educators to improve their job performance.

Keywords: Spiritual, Intelligence, Conflict, Performance, Teachers

Introduction

The motivation behind this learning is to direct research on married female university teachers to see the influence of their spiritual intelligence on their job performance and also to see the influence of spiritual intelligence on their work-family conflict as spiritual intelligence assumes a significant part in job performance and to see the influence of work-family conflict by job performance of married female college instructors. Education is responsible for the success and failure of every society and mostly the educational system everywhere in the world is based upon its teachers. Teachers should be given more attention to make a successful society. [Hom, Sanders & Wright \(1997\)](#) also emphasized that educational systems can only be improved by enlightening the efficacy of teachers as they perform a very major part in escorting the students and refining them. There are a lot of factors that are responsible for affecting teaching and one of them is teachers' spiritual intelligence ([Marghzar & Marzban, 2018](#)). In 2000, Zohar and Marshall stated that spiritual intelligence is responsible for solving our everyday problems for giving meaning and value to life, is responsible for giving meaning to our actions ([Ghosh, 2017](#)). The spiritual intelligence concept emerged because of integrating intelligence with spirituality. As indicated by ([Zohar & Marshall, 2000](#)) spiritual intelligence encourages relationships between effect and feeling and between body and psyche ([Ghosh, 2017](#)). Spiritual intelligence can also be described as the adaptive usage of spiritual material to resolve regular life complications and is the course of accomplishing goals ([Karimi, 2015](#)) Spiritual intelligence is responsible for stimulating the competencies and abilities of the realistic soul or the self, in the form of consideration, insight, joy, peace, love, and creativeness is a higher dimension of intelligence. Deeper meaning and sense of purpose result due to spiritual intelligence, combining enhancements in a widespread series of significant work talents and life abilities ([Griffiths & Kuss, 2011](#))

One can dream and strive due to spiritual intelligence. Work-family conflict causes a great deal of negative outcomes like health problems, and poor work performance and both genders are equally prone to work-family conflict despite the element that women are progressively defenseless against double job conflict between their family job and their job performance. According to [Greenhaus & Beutell \(1985\)](#), it might be clarified that in the shape of inter-role conflict inside the job burdens commencing the tasks and personal realms are commonly inconsistent in some regards. Work comprehensive quality is a significant reason for work-family conflict. It profoundly influences people's proficient, social, and mental physiognomies. Work-family conflict can be portrayed as the communal intrusion of tasks and family roles and causes major subjective and organizational problems ([Erdamar & Demirel, 2013](#)). There are various ways to describe performance. Achieving or accomplishing a given task could be performance. Job performance is the grade by which a distinct executes his given mission according to the organizational standard. A substantial positive correlation has been observed between employee productivity and SI in areas of industrial work and affects the transcendental style of leadership. In organizations where spiritual experiences are facilitated, performance is better. Motekallem introduced that Spiritual intelligence also affects teachers, job performance. ([Khandan, Eyni, & Koohpaei, 2016](#)). A rise in the phenomenon known as "dual-career household syndrome" forces workers to increasingly balance work and family responsibilities at the same time, posing challenges for both workplace performance and family role conflicts. ([Majekodunmi, 2017](#)). Little attention is paid to the association between job satisfaction, job performance, and the spiritual intelligence of the teachers ([Kulshrestha & Singhal, 2017](#)). The motivation behind this study was to look at the connection between spiritual intelligence, such as some of the internal issues of people and their job

performance with their work-family conflict as no research has been conducted in Pakistan on teachers studying their spiritual intelligence and its correlation with job performance & work-family conflict. Married female university teachers face several complications in corresponding and maintaining their professional & personal lives. Inclusive data on teachers' job performance is given by this study and accordingly, it will demonstrate a motivating force for educators to improve their job performance. So, a current study assessed the impact of spiritual intelligence on work conflict & its link with the job performance of university teachers.

Theoretical Framework

King (2008) believes that spiritual intelligence in an individual makes a remarkable ability to comprehend and significance through the duration of regular day-to-day existence and to accomplish a higher spiritual position, as indicated by his four-factor model of spiritual intelligence. The components of this model are: 1. Basic reflection about issues of existence: basic thinking limit about the mystical and existential subjects, for example, in reality, the world, demise, and so on; 2. Generation of individual importance: the capacity to utilize physical and mental encounters to make individual significance and reason; 3. Mystical consciousness: the dimensions to identify parts of otherworldly the world, identity, and others utilizing awareness; 4. Create condition of consciousness: the ability to login to a higher spiritual status, including significant reflection, supplication, examination, and leave it. Moreover, according to Emmons (2000) constituents of spiritual intelligence, five constituents including the dimensions to transcend, the capability to experience discriminating conditions of perception, the skill to participate in daily accomplishments, occasions, and associations with an intellect of the dedicated, the skill to apply spiritual methods to resolve complications in life, also the capability to take part in righteous activities (to

display mercy, to express gratefulness, to endure modestly, to show empathy) helps and allow individuals to resolve difficulties and achieve their objectives in daily lives. Course learning on the work-family-conflict goes hind to the examination carried out (Kahn et. al., 1964) on title role theory. As determined by which role conflict is the load coming about because of concern accomplished by an individual to fix to another role hinder modifications to a role or at the end of the day, from the scale of accepting at least two roles simultaneously. Role theory is a perception in human knowledge & societal mind examination that accepts a huge part of common activity exit the keep on of publicly represented sessions (e.g., mother, boss, teacher). Each job has a great deal of rights, commitments, wants, models, and practices that an individual needs to stand up to and fulfill. The model relies upon the discernment that people carry on in a foreseen way, and that an individual's lead is setting unequivocal, considering social position and various segments. The setting is a moral story consistently used to depict role theory (Erdamar & Demirel, 2013). Research was conducted (Kulshrestha & Singhal, 2017) to examine spirituality in work and to find just how spirituality better professors' performance and institutions' efficacy. The qualitative research method was applied, and information was assembled through interaction with school teachers and from personal observation. Results suggested that spirituality is beneficial for teachers and supports institutions' performance while improving job satisfaction. (Majekodunmi, 2017) Investigated the relations between family-work-conflict and work-family conflict and job performance of 255 employed mothers. The outcomes show, that there exists a positive significant correlation between family work conflict; work-family conflict & job performance of employed mothers. The research was conducted (Ilyas & Arshad, 2017) to inquire about the association of work-family conflict, psychological distress & spiritual intelligence between teachers in universities. The sample of

100 (50 females, 50 males) university teachers was employed under the age group of 30 to 50 years using non-probability purposive sampling. Three self-reported questionnaires were used to estimate the research variables & results presented a significant negative relationship between individual meaning invention (a component of spiritual intelligence) and psychological distress. (Banerjee, Pathak, & Yadav, 2019). Conducted research on 216 students to determine the impact of family relationships on spiritual intelligence and the results indicate a positive significant impact of family relationships on spiritual intelligence. Research was carried out (Marghzar & Marzban, 2018) to examine the association between EFL teachers' spiritual intelligence & their discipline of effectiveness. Two self-reported questionnaires were used to assess study variables. A sample of 148 female and male EFL teachers in work distinct environments including private language institutes, schools, and universities in Iran. The results of this study show that there exists a substantial correlation between teacher's spiritual intelligence and teachers' effectiveness. Furthermore, there exists a substantial variance between female & male teachers about their significance production. The study was conducted (Majekodunmi, 2017) to observe the relationship between family-work conflict & work-family conflict and the job performance of employed mothers. The descriptive survey study method was used for the research. In sampling, purposive and random methods were used to take 300 respondents. Three self-reported questionnaires were used to assess the research variables. The outcomes showed, that there existed a positive substantial correlation between family work conflict; work-family conflict & job performance of employed mothers.

Rationale

The capacity to assume an intellectual, docility & approach to the dynamism that arises after somewhat above the self-esteem besides more than me and my daily interest is a sign of

high SQ. when a person contacts inconsistent needs between job and family roles generating contribution in equal roles becomes further arduous in work-family conflict. This inequality creates a clash in the work-life bond. When the time, energy, and behavior demands of a job role conflict with the intimate life role then work-family conflict occurs. Job performance checks whether an individual does his assigned tasks well or not. Since spiritual intelligence is a relatively new field, there aren't many studies on it. Additionally, there aren't many native studies on work-family conflict, most of which looked at this variable from an organizational standpoint. All the evidence, however, points to the fact that people with low spiritual intelligence are more likely to experience stress and perform poorly, whereas people with high spiritual intelligence are generally healthier, better able to manage stress, and more capable of carrying out their tasks. There is a strong correlation between work-family conflict and job success via spiritual intelligence. Professionals who struggle to strike a balance between their personal and professional lives frequently encounter conflicts that cause them to feel distressed psychologically and negatively impact their performance at work. Teachers have a significant impact on student's lives, and those with high spiritual intelligence can also assist students learn new concepts related to mindfulness, developing self-awareness, and become more committed to prayer, contemplation, and self-reflection. Work-family conflict is seldom studied in the teaching profession since teachers are thought to be able to devote a lot of their time to their families and have low job commitment requirements. But married female university teachers face several complications in corresponding and maintaining their professional & personal lives. Inclusive data on teachers' job performance will be given by this study and accordingly, it will demonstrate a motivating force for educators to improve their job performance. So the current study aims to assess the impact of spiritual intelligence on

work conflict & its link with the job performance of university teachers.

Objectives

- To observe the relationship of spiritual intelligence with work-family conflict & its effect on job performance.
- Spiritual intelligence & work-family conflict are likely to predict job performance.

Hypotheses

H1: Spiritual intelligence and work-family conflict are likely to predict job performance.

H2: There is a significant relationship between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict, and job performance between married female university teachers.

Materials and method

1. Method

For the present research, a sample size of 200 married female university teachers has been taken from two universities (Lahore College for Women University, and Forman College University) in Lahore, Pakistan. To select the teacher's convenience sampling strategy was used. After getting informed consent they were asked to fill in questionnaires. Their responses were recorded and the statistical package for social science SPSS 26 was used to see the relationship between variables.

2. Data Collection

Meaning in Life Questionnaire- Meaning in Life Questionnaire (Steger et. al., 2006) consisted of 10 items designed to measure the content and meaning of life. Responses are recorded on the 7-point Likert scale. Work-family conflict scale- Work-family conflict scale (Carlson, Kacmar, & Williams, 2000) consisted of 18 items used to measure work-family conflict, and responses are recorded on 5 points Likert scale Job Performance Self-Rating Questionnaire- Job Performance Self-Rating Questionnaire (Amin et. al., 2013) is used to assess teachers' job achievements. It consisted of 25 items and components were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale.

Results

Pearson correlation is used to find a correlation between variables and results indicate a significant relationship between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict, and job performance. There was a significant negative relationship between presence & behavior-based work interference with family. There is a substantial weak correlation between presence & management skills and discipline and regularity. There is a positive moderate correlation between Presence and interpersonal skills. There is a substantial positive weak correlation between search & time-based work intervention with family, strain-based work intervention with family, strain-based family intervention with work, and behavior-based family intervention with work and teaching skills. There is a substantial negative association between search and Behavior-based work intervention with family discipline and regularity. There is a substantial positive strong association between search & interpersonal relations. There is a significant positive association between time-based work intervention with family & management skills. There is a substantial negative association between time-based family intervention with work and management skills. There is a substantial positive association between strain-based work intervention with family & management skills and interpersonal skills. There is a substantial positive association between strain-based family intervention with work & teaching skills and interpersonal skills. There is a substantial positive association between behavior-based work intervention with family and management skills. There is a substantial negative association between behavior-based work intervention with family and interpersonal skills. There is a substantial positive association between behavior-based family intervention with work and management skills. There is a substantial negative association between behavior-based family intervention with work & discipline and regularity. Four separate multiple hierarchal linear regressions were run to test the different dimensions of job

performance between married female university teachers. When the predictors were checked for four dimensions of job performance, all the dimensions of job performance i.e., Management skills, Teaching skills, and interpersonal relations, discipline and regularity had the significant result and a. The result of the current research shows a significant relation between spiritual intelligence (which includes presence and search) and work-family-conflict (which includes time-based work intervention with family, time-based family intervention with work, strain-based work intervention with family, strain-based family intervention with work, behavior-based work intervention with family and behavior-based family intervention with work), work-family conflict and job performance and spiritual intelligence and job performance of married female universities teacher's.

[See Appendix A, B, and C](#)

Discussion

This study investigates the association between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict & job performance of married female university teachers, and Spiritual Intelligence. Work-family Conflict Predicts Job Performance of married female university teachers or not. This chapter emphasizes the discussion of the result. The results are supported by the previous research conducted in Islamic Azad University by [Sisk \(2008\)](#) in which 109 married staff members presented a substantial association between spiritual intelligence and work-family conflict. From the data collected from the married female teachers of Lahore, it was revealed that spiritual intelligence-like presence has a moderate relationship with behavior-based work intervention with family and search has weak association using time-based work intervention with family, strain-based family intervention using work, and behavior-based conflicts. This relationship was expected as research was conducted by ([Erdamar & Demirel, 2013](#)) to examine the family-work-conflict and work-family-conflict and teachers go through and it

was found that young teachers and females went more through work-family conflict and teachers of private school more have gone through all of the conflicts. This research also studied the association between spiritual intelligence & job performance (which includes management skills, teaching skills, interpersonal relations, and discipline and regularity) of married female university teachers' which is in line with the stated hypothesis. However, according to the data collected from the universities in Lahore, Pakistan there is a substantial positive strong association between search & interpersonal relations. The results supported by ([Kimiayai & Daryae, 2016](#)) reveals a substantial positive strong association between spiritual intelligence & emotional intelligence. However, the relationship varies from strong to moderate to weak relationship. ([Len, Jerry, & Robert, 2002](#)) Revealing that enhanced emotional and spiritual intelligence has a positive impact at the personal level on their work success. The study also surveyed the relationship between work-family conflict and job performance. The results showed a weak association between work-family conflict & job performance. Research conducted by ([Warokka & Febrilia, 2015](#)) revealed that work-family conflict is substantially associated using job performance. A study was conducted by [Kates \(2018\)](#) to observe the association between work-family conflict & job performance of nurses and the results indicated a negative effect on the job performance of nurses. The research was presented ([Majekodunmi, 2017](#)) to observe the relationship between family-work-conflict and work-family-conflict and job performance of employed mothers. The outcomes show, that there is a positive substantial correlation between family-work conflict, work-family conflict & job performance of employed women. As per my observation, the results indicated on that point a significant association between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict & job performance of female university teachers, and the relationship varies from strong to moderate to weak. For this many

female married teachers of Lahore undergo a survey. The questionnaire was designed to highlight the differentials and eliminate the invariability, so the responses fall coherent with the research hypothesis that was extracted from the previous research. The previous research highlighted in the literature review of my research report was extracted from credible resources. All of the previous studies were on different segments and all those suggest significant associations between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict & job performance. However, through thorough research, I have identified that no study in this combination of variables was conducted in Pakistan. An in-depth study suggests that my data is a primary form of research, and the outcome of my research is independent of the outcomes from the previous studies due to several highlighted factors e.g. married female university teachers, lecturer & Assistant professors, Regular faculty members working for at least 2 years and several other factors are to be included in further work if the study continue any further. Also, cultural differences, gender differences, and working environment may be the reason for work-family- conflict having a weak relationship with job performance.

Recommendations:

For further studies, data should be taken from male university teachers and moderation analysis should also be performed. Studies should be conducted in the areas of spiritual intelligence and job performance so more evidence should be collected in this area.

Conclusion

This study investigates the link between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict & job performance of married female university teachers & whether Spiritual Intelligence and work-family Conflict predict the Job Performance of married female university teachers or not the outcomes reveal that, there exists a significant association between spiritual intelligence, work-family conflict & job performance of female university teachers and the correlation varies

from strong to moderate to weak and spiritual intelligence & work-family conflict are predictors of job performance.

References

- Amin et. al. (2013). Teachers' Job Performance At Secondary Level. *Gomal University Journal Of Research*, 29(2).
- Banerjee, R., Pathak, R., & Yadav, S. (2019). Family Relationship and Spiritual Intelligence: With Reference to Students of Professional Courses.
- Carlson, D., Kacmar, K., & Williams, L. (2000). Construction and Initial Validation of a Multidimensional Measure of Work-Family Conflict. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 56(2), 249-276. doi:10.1006/jvbe.1999.1713
- Emmons, R. (2000). Is Spirituality an Intelligence? Motivation, Cognition, and the Psychology of Ultimate Concern. *The International Journal for the Psychology of Religion*, 10(1).
- Erdamar, G., & Demirel, H. (2013). Investigation of Work-family, Family-work Conflict of the Teachers. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 116, 4919 – 4924. doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.1050
- Ghosh, S. (2017). Status of Workplace Spiritual Intelligence between Secondary School Teachers. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 7(8). doi:10.21275/ART2019264
- Griffiths, M., & Kuss, D. (2011). Online social networking and addiction--a review of the psychological literature. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 8(9), 3528-52. doi:10.3390/ijerph8093528
- Ilyas, N., & Arshad, T. (2017). Spiritual Intelligence, Work-Family Conflict and Psychological Distress between University Teachers. *Bahria Journal of Professional Psychology*, 16(1), 01-25.
- Karimi, F. (2015). Relationship between spiritual intelligence and job satisfaction between female high school teachers. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 10(6), 739-743. doi:10.5897/ERR2015.2130
- Khandan, M., Eyni, Z., & Koohpaei, A. (2016). Relationship between Spiritual Intelligence

- and Job Performance: A Case Study of Nurses and Nursing Aids in the Main University Hospital of Qom, Iran. *Health Spirituality and Medical Ethics*, 4(3), 8-13.
- Kimiyayi, M., & Daryaei, S. (2016). Relationship between spiritual intelligence, emotional intelligence with occupational performance the guidance school teachers' occupational performance in Shiraz educational system organization. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HUMANITIES AND CULTURAL STUDIES*, 3(2). Retrieved from <http://www.ijhcs.com/index.php/ijhcs/index>
- King, D. B. (2008). RETHINKING CLAIMS OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE: A DEFINITION, MODEL, AND MEASURE(Unpublished Master's Thesis) Trent University, Peterborough, ON. Retrieved from <http://www.davidbking.net/spiritualintelligence/thesis.pdf>
- Kulshrestha, S., & Singhal, T. (2017). IMPACT OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE ON PERFORMANCE AND JOB SATISFACTION: A STUDY ON SCHOOL TEACHERS. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 44(2), 2349-3593. doi:10.5281/zenodo.343742
- Len, T., Jerry, B., & Robert, M. (2002). Linking emotional intelligence, spirituality and workplace performance: Definitions, models and ideas for research. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 17(3), 203–218. doi:10.1108/02683940210423114
- Majekodunmi, A. (2017). Work-family-conflict and family-work-conflict as correlates of job performance between working mothers: implications for industrial social workers. *African Journal of Social Work*, 7(1).
- Marghzar, S., & Marzban, A. (2018). The Relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and Efficacy between Iranian EFL Teachers. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 8(1), 67-73. doi:10.17507/tpls.0801.09
- Steger et. al. (2006). The meaning in life questionnaire: Assessing the presence of and search for meaning in life. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 53(1), 80-93. doi:10.1037/0022-0167.53.1.80
- Warokka, A., & Febrilia, I. (2015). Work-Family Conflict and Job Performance: Lesson from a Southeast Asian Emerging Market. *Journal of Southeast Asian Research*, 14. doi:10.5171/2015.420802
- Zohar, D., & Marshall, I. (2000). *Spiritual Intelligence - SQ: The Ultimate Intelligence* London: Bloomsbury. Retrieved from <http://www.books.google.com>

Appendix A**Table 1:** Descriptive demographics of subjects

Variables	M (SD)	f (%)
Age	36.15(4.10)	
Type of university		
Private		72(36.0)
Government		128(64.0)
Designation		
Professor		76(38.0)
Assistant professor		33(16.5)
Lecturer		91(45.5)
Years of education	19.18(1.64)	
Total years of teaching experience		
2-3		30(15.0)
4-6		67(33.5)
7-9		97(48.5)
10-12		6(3.0)
Total years of teaching experience within this university		
2-3		93(46.5)
4-6		40(20.0)
7-9		67(33.5)
Physical disability		
No		200(100)

Appendix B**Table 2:** Psychometrics properties of major study variables in the sample (N=200)

Variables	K	M	SD	A	Skewness	Kurtosis
1. Meaning in life	10	32.8440	8.925	.800	-.827	-.646
2. Work-family conflict	18	57.316	6.595	.704	.337	.389
3. Teacher's job performance	25	96.927	6.739	.700	.293	-.991

Note, α = Cronbach alpha, k = No of items, SD = Standard Deviation, M = Mean

Results in the table suggest that the distribution is approximately normally distributed since the value of skewness and kurtosis is within +/- 1.96, indicating that the data is approximately normally distributed. Cronbach alpha values for all the subscales can also be seen in the table.

Appendix C

Table 3: Correlation between Spiritual Intelligence & Work-family Conflict & Job Performance of Married Female University Teachers.

Measure	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1- Presence	—											
2- Search	.332**	—										
3- Time-based work intervention with family	.117	.219**	—									
4- Time-based family intervention with work	-.061	-.137	-.240**	—								
5- Strain-based work intervention with family	.102	.155*	.306**	.066	—							
6- Strain-based family intervention with work	-.061	.217**	-.231**	.418	.241**	—						
7- Behavior-based work intervention with family	-.388**	-.282**	.119	.008	-.101	.249*	—					
8- Behavior-based family intervention with work	-.114	.256**	.389**	-.078	.498**	.324*	.148*	—				
9- Teaching skills	-.106	.166*	-.058	-.032	.034	.186*	.009	.037	—			
10- Management skills	-.255**	.089	.271**	-.191*	.297**	-.004	.214**	.268**	.403*	—		
11- Discipline and regularity	-.211**	-.226**	-.005	.105	.107	-.035	-.039	-.226**	.198*	.240*	—	
12- Interpersonal relations	.375**	.678**	.084	-.084	.288**	.145*	-.287**	.080	.349*	.278*	-.006	—

Note: **p>.01, *p>.05, ***p>.001